

INTRODUCTION

Modern organizations face rapid changes in the market environment. Hierarchy simplification allows for faster response to change, local decision-making, and adaptation to new conditions. Flat structures also promote better communication between levels, which makes employees feel more involved in decision-making. This can lead to increased motivation and productivity.

Reducing management levels can lead to lower administrative costs by reducing the number of management staff and bureaucracy. However, a reduction in levels should not mean a loss of the organization's overall capacity. This is achieved through the adequate allocation of roles and responsibilities and the effective use of technology to support collaboration.

Thus, the relevance of the topic lies in the need to better meet the challenges of modern business while ensuring the preservation and even strengthening of the company's internal potential.

The article aims to reflect the results of the mathematical modeling of rational hierarchy in the organizational structure of public administration, using the customs authority as an example.

The achievement of this goal will provide proof of a set of measures related to the transition from hierarchical to flat structures in digitalization conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study materials were articles from periodical scientific publications, such as the *Journal of Organization Design*, *Eurasian Business Review*, *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering*, and *Small Business Economics*.

Queuing theory is a mathematical theory that aims to study queuing systems (QSs), which are the subject of its research.

QSs are systems designed to be reusable in performing homogeneous tasks [12].

The purpose of queuing theory is to develop recommendations on the rational construction of QSs, the logical organization of their work, and the regulation of the flow of applications to ensure high efficiency of QS functioning [Ibid].

In the study of customs problems, queuing theory was applied exclusively to analyze the functioning of customs posts and checkpoints when conducting customs control at the grassroots level over goods moving across the customs border [13]. In this regard,

the main provisions of queuing theory were not applied to the study of the hierarchy of customs structures. For this reason, studying the evolution of customs structures using QS tools is a relevant direction of developing applied aspects of queuing theory.

Like any state body, the customs authority has a hierarchical structure, i.e., several subordination levels. From the standpoint of queuing theory, the organizational structure of the customs authority is a multi-channel (C-channel) QS, in which C is the number of hierarchical levels. Customs authorities exercise customs control over goods crossing the customs border. In general, the flow of goods entering and leaving the customs territory cannot be restricted from the point of view of queuing theory. In this sense, the service discipline of the customs authority is defined by an unlimited queue of goods; in this regard, the organizational structure of the customs authority, taking into account this classification feature, is a QS with an unlimited queue. Thus, the organizational structure of the customs authority should be classified as a C-channel QS with an unlimited queue.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the digital transformation of state institutions and commercial organizations, the fundamental systemic problem is building an adequate (rational, efficient, or optimal) organizational structure or reforming the existing one. The problem is universal since it involves transforming a hierarchical structure into a flat one in almost every specific case.

C. Markides writes that managers must delegate decision-making authority to their employees and give them more autonomy in flat structures. However, certain boundary-setting or fencing parameters must be established for such highly delegated regimes to work to guide employees' decisions and actions [1].

M. Reitzig relates different types of flat structures to goals such as corporate creativity, speed, and talent attraction and retention. The author addresses the issue of how various highly delegated settings serve different corporate goals [2].

M. McCaffrey notes that while flat organizations sometimes perform well in relatively defined and stable environments, they struggle with innovation, scale, and longevity in more dynamic and time-sensitive situations. In contrast, the management hierarchy performs valuable economic functions by solving coordination and collaboration problems and providing a structure where employees can make decisions [3].

M. Reitzig gives an example of an organization that has grown from eight to about 70 employees and, as of 2021, uses a flat structure to manage company operations [4].

The author also shows that flat structures, regardless of their exact nature and the type of personnel working, reach natural limits when scaled [5].

O. Sorenson offers some criticisms on why managers may benefit from simplifying their companies [6]. M. Reitzig writes that flat structures can both succeed and fail. Operating without middle managers increases the workload for employees and the remaining managers [7]. G. Mustafa et al. studied which structural organization is more suitable for taking advantage of digitalization [8].

O. Baumann and B. Wu write that unlike industrial firms of the past, which had both large scale and scope, today's digital firms tend to have an even larger scale (hyperscaling) but a much narrower scope (hyperspecialization). The authors question whether flat organizations are simply exceptions, perhaps more appropriate only for certain firms in specific industries or suitable only for part of a larger organization, such as a team implementing a particular initiative [9].

N. Ivanov et al. presented the author's concept of applying the methods of system analysis and synthesis, organizational management theory, and organizational modeling to create a rational organizational structure corresponding to the specifics of newly created small construction organizations. The authors confirmed the hypothesis about the possibility of forming a sensible management system for a small construction organization by transforming the organizational structure considering the mechanism of its management. The assumption that the effective organizational structure depends on the company's primary activity type is also confirmed [10].

A. F. Cortes and A. N. Kiss write that flatter organizational structures typical of small firms may allow managers to perceive a broader range of available strategic choices. However, higher resource availability may limit this perception. In turn, higher resource availability may enable managers to perceive a more remarkable ability to implement strategic actions. Nevertheless, this perception may be more limited in firms with flatter organizational structures. In addition, ownership concentration is a factor in this relationship [11].

Thus, flat management structures in an organization have many pluses that contribute to efficiency and innovation. These include speeding up decision-making, increasing flexibility, increasing employee engagement, reducing costs, improving communication, and stimulating creativity and initiative.

The purpose of the study is to develop a mathematical model to justify a rational hierarchy in the organizational structure of a government agency (using the customs agency as an example).

The objectives of the study are:

- 1) to identify the tendency of change in the average time of stay of a commodity lot in the service system of the customs authority while reducing the number of hierarchical levels of its organizational structure and preserving the overall potential of the organization;

2) to identify the tendency of change in the average time of stay of the goods lot in the service system of the customs authority when the number of hierarchical levels of its organizational structure is reduced, and the overall potential of the organization is changed.

RESULTS

Table 1 describes the QS model for studying the main parameters of the management organizational structure, using the customs authorities as an example.

Table 1

Main parameters of the organizational structure of the state body as a queuing system

Indicator name	Unit of measurement	Indicator (calculation formula)
Number of hierarchical levels of the customs authority	units	C
Potential of the customs authority (this study considered the human resource potential of the customs authority, represented by its staffing level)	staff units	M
Absolute throughput capacity of the customs authority (average number of consignments for which the customs authority is able to carry out customs control in 1 hour)	consignments/hour	$A = \lambda q = \lambda$
Relative throughput capacity of the customs authority (probability that the customs authority will perform customs control)	–	$q = 1$
Intensity of consignments (average number of consignments arriving at the customs office in 1 hour)	consignments/hour	λ
Intensity of customs control over a consignment by the i -th hierarchical level of the customs authority (average number of consignments subject to customs control by the i -th hierarchical level of the customs authority in 1 hour)	consignments/hour	μ_i
Total intensity of customs control with respect to a consignment by the customs authority (average number of consignments with respect to which customs control is performed by the customs authority in 1 hour)	consignments/hour	$\sum_{i=1}^c \mu_i$
Average intensity of customs control with respect to a consignment by a customs authority (average number of consignments with respect to which customs control is performed by one hierarchical level of the customs authority in 1 hour)	consignments/hour	$\bar{\mu} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^c \mu_i}{C}$
Average time of customs control with respect to one consignment by the customs authority	hours	$t_{cc} = \frac{1}{\bar{\mu}}$
Customs authority workload coefficient (average share of time during which the customs authority is busy with customs control)	–	$W_q = \frac{L_q}{\lambda}$
Customs workload ratio (the average proportion of time a customs office is busy conducting customs control)	–	$\rho = \frac{\lambda}{\bar{\mu}}$

The probability that all hierarchical levels of the customs authority are not busy with customs control operations	-	$P_0 = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{C-1} \frac{\rho^n}{n!} + \frac{\rho^C}{C! \left[1 - \left(\frac{\rho}{C} \right) \right]} \right)^{-1}$
The probability that there are n lots of goods in the service system of the customs authority	-	$\begin{cases} P_n = \frac{\rho^n}{n!} P_0, 0 < n \leq C; \\ P_n = \frac{\rho^n}{C! C^{n-C}} P_0, n > C. \end{cases}$
Average number of consignments in the queue	consignments	$L_q = \left[\frac{C\rho}{(C-\rho)^2} \right] P_C$
Average number of consignments in the customs service system	consignments	$L_s = L_q + \rho$
Average time a consignment stays in the queue	hours	$W_q = \frac{L_q}{\lambda}$
Average time a consignment of goods stays in the customs service system	hours	$W_s = W_q + t_{cc}$

Note: Compiled by the authors based on [12].

Modeling of the rational hierarchical organizational structure of a state body

Statement of task 1: to determine the average time of stay of the goods lot in the service system (W_s) for the customs authority at different numbers of hierarchical levels ($C = 5, 4, 3$) under the following conditions:

- the intensity of goods consignment arrival (λ) is equal to 50 goods consignments per hour;
- the absolute throughput capacity of the customs authority (A) is equal to 50 consignments per hour;
- the capacity of the customs authority (M) is equal to 100 staff units;
- the total intensity of customs control of a consignment by the customs authority ($\sum_{i=1}^C \mu_i$) is equal to 150 consignments per hour;
- otherwise, n (number of consignments in the queue) $\rightarrow \infty$.

The results of the analysis of the efficiency of the functioning of the organizational structure of the customs authority depending on the change in the number of hierarchical levels make it possible to identify the trend reflected in Figure 1.

Compiled by the authors based on the calculations made.

Note:

x-axis: 5-level hierarchical structure,

4-level hierarchical structure,

3-level hierarchical structure;

y-axis: number of product batches per hour, number of staff units.

Figure 1 Trend of W_s changes when the number of hierarchical levels in the organizational structure of the customs authority decreases

The tendency of change in the average time of stay of a goods lot in the service system of the customs authority is such that the average time of stay of a goods lot in the service system of the customs authority (W_s) decreases with the preservation of the intensity of goods lot arrival (λ), the absolute throughput capacity of the customs authority (A), the potential of the customs authority (M), and, as a consequence, the overall intensity of customs control over the goods lot by the customs authority ($\sum_{i=1}^C \mu_i$), provided that the number of hierarchical levels (C) is reduced.

Statement of task 2: Determine the average dwell time of a consignment in the service system (W_s) for a customs authority with three hierarchical levels ($C = 3$) with a modified capacity of the customs authority (M).

For the comparability of the results obtained when solving task 1 and task 2, the corresponding change in the potential will be made according to the following rule. When reducing one of the hierarchical levels (for example, the 3rd hierarchical level in the model of the 4-level organizational structure presented in Figure 2), the total potential of the customs authority will be reduced by the amount of the potential characteristic of this level.

Compiled by the authors.

Figure 2 The model of the 4-level organizational structure of the customs authority management

Thus, the potential of the customs authority, in this case, will be 0.8M or 80 staff units, which will change in the same proportion and equal 120 commodity lots per hour.

The following indicators remain constant (const):

- the intensity of goods consignments arrival (λ) is equal to 50 goods consignments per hour;
- the absolute throughput of the customs office (A) is equal to 50 consignments per hour.
- otherwise, n (number of consignments in the queue) $\rightarrow \infty$.

The results of the comparative analysis of the efficiency of the functioning of the organizational structure of the customs authority depending on the reduction of the customs authority's total capacity make it possible to fix the signs of the trend, graphically presented in Figure 3.

Compiled by the authors based on calculations made by the authors.

Figure 3 The trend of W_s changes when the total potential of the customs authority decreases

The tendency of change in the average time of stay of the goods lot in the system of service of the customs authority is such that with the preservation of the intensity of arrival of goods lots (λ) and the absolute throughput capacity of the customs authority (A), but the reduction of the potential of the customs authority (M) and, as a consequence, the total intensity of customs control about the goods lot by the customs authority ($\sum_{i=1}^c \mu_i$), the average time of stay of the goods lot in the system of service of the customs authority (W_s) increases, which determines the ineffectiveness of the reduction in W_s in the system of service of the customs authority.

In connection with the above, the transition from a hierarchical organizational structure to a flat structure, carried out in the conditions of digital transformation, is most rational in compliance with the following system-forming principle – the principle of the integrity of capacity: a reduction in the number of hierarchical levels in the organizational structure should be carried out while maintaining the overall capacity of the organization because the time in the service system (W_s) in this case is reduced to the greatest extent. A reduction in capacity in the transformation process inevitably leads to a decrease in the system's efficiency.

DISCUSSION

Reducing the number of hierarchical levels in the organization structure has several key perspectives that can improve the company's overall capacity.

We agree with M. Shaw et al. that reducing levels helps to speed up decision-making and improves information sharing between different departments [14]. This creates a more transparent environment and allows employees to respond to changes rapidly.

A flat structure enables faster adaptation to changes in the market or within the company [15]. This is critical in a highly competitive and rapidly changing technology.

When employees are given more responsibility, their motivation and engagement levels increase [16]. They feel more important, and their contributions are more valued.

Fewer layers of management means lower management costs. This allows resources to be reallocated to more critical areas, such as product development or improving customer service.

Flat structures often contribute to faster results because teams have more autonomy and less bureaucracy.

Thus, exploring the topic of reducing hierarchical levels provides many opportunities to improve organizations' overall effectiveness and capacity.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the flatter the organizational structure of a public body, the more effective its time performance in providing public services to clients (consumers) in the public body's service system.

The presented methodology and the results of its approbation using the example of customs structures make it possible to assert that the flat organizational structure is more rational than the hierarchical one. First of all, the speed of servicing clients' requests in such a structure increases due to the reduction of internal inter-level communication links.

The transition to a flat structure should be based on the principle of integrity of the system's potential, and the chosen transition strategy depends mainly on the degree of digital and service transformation of government agencies. The introduction of digital technologies and services, automation and intellectualization of the factory bodies' activities increase the efficiency of managerial decision-making but also require changes in the dynamics of management, which is provided by flat structures at the system level.

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